

**glycan
trigger**

D5.6 – Project website

WP5

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Legal disclaimer

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ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	Definition
CD	Crohn's disease
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General data protection regulation
GI	Gastrointestinal
HADEA	European Health and Digital Executive Agency
IBD	Inflammatory bowel disease
WP	Work Package

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About the project

GlycanTrigger is a project funded by the European Union, within the Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Actions (RIA). The long-term goal of GlycanTrigger is to unlock a new checkpoint that regulates health to chronic inflammation transition by proposing mucosa glycans modifications as a master switch towards the early perturbation of host-microbial interactions and the consequent activation of both innate and humoral immune systems. Ultimately, we want to intercept or revert this master switch and thereby exploit/analyse whether this constitutes an opportunity to prevent the development of chronic inflammation in at-risk individuals.

Chronic inflammation is the underlying cause of numerous diseases, including Crohn's disease (CD), which may have a preclinical phase with immunological changes occurring before symptoms manifest. To improve disease prediction and prevention, our innovative approach seeks to understand the health-to-intestinal inflammation transition using CD as a disease model. The GlycanTrigger project will investigate when, why and how changes in glycosylation at the surface of the gut mucosa, constitute an early trigger of the health-to-inflammation transition. We will address how changes in glycosylation of the gut mucosa act as a primary event that dysregulates not only local mechanisms, but also systemic mechanisms associated with health to inflammation transition. Although high-risk/high-gain, our project is based on appropriate and long-standing expertise and fundamental biological principles that the consortium has helped establish and is thus likely to lead to (i) breakthrough biomedical concepts in the driving factors that trigger the health to chronic inflammation transition and to (ii) novel predictive tools for early detection of at-risk individuals to develop chronic inflammation, as well as to (iii) a novel intervention strategy that will be tested for disease prevention. In the longer term, the results of GlycanTrigger will improve health literacy through better-informed management of health status, diet and life-style to maintain a healthy gut. Our strategy for understanding the transition from health to gut inflammation is comprehensive and includes the impact of mucosa glycans on local and systemic mechanisms.

Partners:

I3S (Coordinator)	I3S - INSTITUTO DE INVESTIGACAO E INOVACAO EM SAUDE DA UNIVERSIDADE DO PORTO (Portugal)
LUMC	ACADEMISCH ZIEKENHUIS LEIDEN (The Netherlands)
SORBONNE	SORBONNE UNIVERSITÉ (France)
CHARITE	CHARITE - UNIVERSITAETSMEDIZIN BERLIN (Germany)
GLSMED LH	GLSMED LEARNING HEALTH SA (Portugal)
MOUNT SINAI	ICAHN SCHOOL OF MEDICINE AT MOUNT SINAI (USA)
EFCCA	EUROPEAN FEDERATION OF CROHN'S AND ULCERATIVE COLITIS ASSOCIATIONS (Belgium)
SPI	SOCIEDADE PORTUGUESA DE INOVACÃO CONSULTADORIA EMPRESARIAL E FOMENTO DA INOVACÃO SA (Portugal)
LUD	LUDGER LIMITED (United Kingdom)

Executive Summary

The present document intends to provide a general overview of the structure and contents of the GlycanTrigger project website as the main digital communication channel of the project. It includes, at the time of writing this report, the current status and the planned content and features evolution that will be developed along with the project progress during the 6 years lifespan. This is a living and dynamic platform which content is constantly update throughout the time of execution of GlycanTrigger project.

The website includes a public section dedicated to general non-confidential information with project description, consortium information, links to project dissemination and communication events, as well as a public repository of non-confidential project materials (e.g., public deliverables). It also includes a section dedicated to patients, where up-to-date information about the disease will be shared.

Chapter 1

Introduction

1. Introduction

The GlycanTrigger website was designed as the main hub of information to make the project, its context and motivation, as well as its technical progress widely visible. The present document provides an overview about the project website structure and content.

The website will provide detailed information about GlycanTrigger objectives and activities and is intended for public outreach and dissemination of the project outcomes. This will be the main communication channel of the project and will be continuously updated with materials, like summaries of consortium meetings, news about upcoming meetings or any project-related events, dissemination actions, publications, communication materials (e.g., news, newsletters, photos), as well as Inflammatory Bowel Diseases (IBDs)-related information. The website targets very distinct audiences, which are characterised in detail in Deliverable 5.1 - Dissemination, Communication & Exploitation Plan 1, namely project partners, stakeholders, the wider public and the press/media.

The website is available at the following domain: www.glycantrigger.eu and will:

- **Present the project**, including information about GlycanTrigger, its goals, vision and mission, the consortium's partners and all involved teams;
- **Provide information about IBDs**, including the specific conditions onto which the project focuses, and useful links for patients, families and the general public;
- **Promote project results and outputs**, including events and activities, scientific and medical publications, infographics, factsheets, relevant materials for partners and stakeholders, etc;
- **Merge and market other communication channels and tools**, including social media (feed), press releases, external events, and newsletters.

Moreover, the website contains essential aspects such as the EU emblem, funding acknowledgment, disclaimer, privacy policy, contacts, and social media handles. In regard to maintenance, the website will be continuously updated by SPI in straight articulation with the coordinator (i3S), in line with the developments associated with the progress of project activities.

It is worth mentioning that during a first period of website development, a project public landing page was made available, which included the basic information about the project, as shown in Figure 1.

GlycanTrigger

Glycans as master triggers of health to intestinal inflammation transition

About the project

GlycanTrigger is a project funded by the European Union within the **Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Actions**, bringing together **9 organisations from 6 different European countries and 1 non-European country (USA)**.

In GlycanTrigger, we will investigate when, why and how changes in gut glycome trigger health to chronic inflammation transition.

The project started in January 2023 and **will be developed for 6 years under the coordination of Instituto de Investigação e Inovação em Saúde (I3S)** from the University of Porto, Portugal. The GlycanTrigger consortium includes representatives from medical universities and research centers, clinical centers, one biotechnology company, one consultancy company, and one European patients' association.

Consortium partners

I3S INSTITUTO DE INVESTIGAÇÃO E INOVAÇÃO EM SAÚDE UNIVERSIDADE DO PORTO

LMC Leiden University Medical Center

SORBONNE UNIVERSITÉ

CHARITÉ UNIVERSITÄT MEDIZINISCHES KOLLEGE BERLIN

HOSPITAL DA LUZ LEARNING HEALTH

Icahn School of Medicine at Mount Sinai

EFCCA EUROPEAN FEDERATION OF COLLAGEN AND GLYCOSAMINOGLYCAN RESEARCHERS

spi Sociedade Portuguesa de Inovação

Ludger

 Coordinator contacts

For more information, please contact:
 Salomé Pinho, Project Coordinator
 Instituto de Investigação e Inovação em Saúde (I3S), Portugal
 Email: salomep@i3s.up.pt

Funded by the European Union

Figure 1. GlycanTrigger initial landing page (provisional)

The full website is publicly available by the end of April (M4) and is described in more detail in the upcoming section.

Chapter 2

Project website

2. Project website

Given the early stage of the technical progress of the project, only the generic pages describing the objectives, motivation, vision and mission of the project and the consortium overview are populated. The website structure is provided in Figure 2. As soon as available, additional publications, non-confidential deliverables, and materials dedicated to patient empowerment and health literacy will be added. The website is a living platform and will be updated regularly based on the communication and dissemination plan driven by WP5 and described in detail under the framework of Deliverable D5.1.

Figure 2. GlycanTrigger website structure

All sections of the website have the GlycanTrigger logo at the top and the acknowledgement of funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme (a flag and a text in line with the requirements from the European Commission) as well as the reference details of the main contact person (project coordinator) of GlycanTrigger at the bottom of the website. Privacy Policy can be found at the footer of the website. A link to the main home page is included and accessible from all 5 sub-pages on the top of the website (by clicking on GlycanTrigger logo). The website is responsive to the browser, making it also readable from mobile devices.

Additionally, the website footer includes links to all other online channels of the project, i.e., social media accounts, which currently include Twitter, LinkedIn and Instagram.

2.1 Homepage

The homepage of the website represents the central message of GlycanTrigger in regard to communicating what the project is about and why it is important, as well as its most recent activities. The homepage is designed according to the following structure:

- Top of the page (Figure 3):
 - Branding of GlycanTrigger (Logo and background image – still to be included);
 - Menu items: About; Our Research; Education and Training; Patient Area; Media & Events;
 - Slideshow with relevant questions and answers (see section 2.1.1);
 - Search button;
- Central part of the page:
 - Most recent news and events;
 - About GlycanTrigger, including short description and brief information;
- Bottom of the page:
 - Slider with logos of consortium partners;
 - Contact information;
 - “Subscribe newsletter” form;
 - Social media buttons (Twitter, LinkedIn and Instagram);
 - Horizon Europe funding disclaimer.

Figure 3. GlycanTrigger homepage

2.1.1 Slideshow

The slideshow (Figure 4) is presented at the top of the homepage and addresses key questions to allow any website visitor to understand what is addressed in this online communication channel. It is intended to provide definitions of basic concepts underlying the research and motivation behind GlycanTrigger and to explain what is GlycanTrigger and why the project is innovative and important.

What are Inflammatory bowel diseases (IBD)?

IBDs are clinical conditions characterised by uncontrolled inflammation of the digestive tract and include two idiopathic and incurable diseases: Crohn's disease (CD) and ulcerative colitis (UC).

...

What are Glycans?

Glycans, also called polysaccharides, are sugar chains that serve several functions in our bodies (structural, energy storage, and regulatory functions). The array of glycans in our gut (the glycome) plays an important role in the correct function and protection of our gut and its balanced interaction with microorganisms.

...

What is the GlycanTrigger project?

GlycanTrigger is a project funded by the European Union that looks into how changes in glycans (the sugar chains) on the surface of the gut can cause inflammation in the body. The project introduces the idea of "glycan mimicry" which means that some molecules can trick our immune system and start the inflammation process.

...

Why is GlycanTrigger's approach different?

GlycanTrigger is testing the innovative hypothesis that changes in glycans composition of the protective layer of our gut (the glycocalyx) act as an early event of the inflammatory response. This can cause a shift in the way sugar is used in the body, which can lead to an imbalance in the bacteria living in our gut (i.e., the gut microbiome).

...

Figure 4. GlycanTrigger homepage slideshow

2.1.2 Recent activities

The homepage will display, in its central part, the most recent news about project achievements, participation in conferences, summaries of consortium meetings or project-related events, publications, etc. It will also announce upcoming project-related events (e.g., webinars, training sessions). Figure 5 shows the visual aspect of this section when populated with news and events. The content shown is provisional and will be completed during project implementation. This section will allow any visitor to see the most recent developments of the project.

Figure 5. Homepage “Latest news” and “Events”

2.1.3 About the project and the consortium

The homepage includes a brief description about the project (Figure 6), providing context to the rest of the website. This short section addresses the research and innovation nature of GlycanTrigger and explains briefly the multidisciplinary and international background of the project.

Additionally, the logos of the consortium partners are also displayed at the bottom of the homepage (Figure 7). The footer includes the main contact, subscribe buttons and EU funding acknowledgement.

About – GlycanTrigger

GlycanTrigger is a project funded by the European Union within the **Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Actions**, bringing together **9 organisations from 6 different European countries and 1 non-European country (USA)**.

In GlycanTrigger, we will investigate when, why and how changes in gut glycome trigger health to chronic inflammation transition.

The project started in January 2023 and will be developed for 6 years under the coordination of Instituto de Investigação e Inovação em Saúde (i3S) from the University of Porto, Portugal. The GlycanTrigger consortium includes representatives from medical universities and research centers, clinical centers, one biotechnology company, one consultancy company, and one European patients' association.

Budget

6.8 M€

Duration

72 months

9 partners

6 European countries
1 USA

Diseases

Crohn's disease (CD)
Ulcerative Colitis (UC)

Figure 6. Short description “About” GlycanTrigger in the homepage

Contact Info

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[Privacy Policy](#)

Subscribe Newsletter

Subscribe to our newsletter to receive news and updates about the Glycan Trigger project. For more information please see our Privacy policy.

Social Media

[Instagram](#)
[Twitter](#)
[LinkedIn](#)

Disclaimer

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Figure 7. GlycanTrigger consortium slider and website footer

2.2 'About' page

This section includes all the background information about the project:

- Short description (Figure 8);
- Scope of the project, which addresses the challenges, hypothesis, methodology and impacts in the format of questions and answers (Figure 9);
- A summary of GlycanTrigger technical objectives (Figure 10);
- A short description of each partner organisation and its role in the project (Figure 11)
- An overview of the work plan and short description of each WP (Figure 12)
- A description of expected impacts of the project at the scientific/technological, economic and societal levels (Figure 13).

Figure 8. “About” section of the GlycanTrigger website

Figure 9. Scope of the project in the “About” section of the GlycanTrigger website

Objectives

GlycanTrigger wants to find a way to **stop chronic inflammation** from happening by studying changes in the way glycans attach to the lining of the gut. There is a hypothesis that these changes can start a process that activates the body's immune system and causes inflammation. The **project long-term goal** is to figure out how to turn off this process and see if it can help prevent chronic inflammation in individuals who are at risk for it.

To achieve the long-term goal, GlycanTrigger will follow the specific objectives presented below:

- **Define** the gut glycome map during the transition from health to chronic inflammation.
- **Investigate** how changes in gut glycocalyx impact microbial and immunological dynamics, leading to dysbiosis and inflammation.
- **Explore** how changes in gut mucosa glycans activate both innate and humoral immune responses
- **Demonstrate** the therapeutical potential of glyco-metabolic remodelling in preventing the shift from health to inflammation
- **Maximize** the societal impact through targeted dissemination, communication, and engagement with relevant stakeholders, towards improving health literacy and empowering patients for disease prevention.

Figure 10. Objectives of the project in the “About” section of the GlycanTrigger website

Consortium

Instituto de Investigação e Inovação em Saúde (i3S) merges three institutes and researchers from several schools of the University of Porto, thus consolidating an extensive collaboration between all institutions spanning many years. i3S aims to face and overcome the most relevant health challenges society faces today, such as ageing, infectious diseases, cancer, regenerative medicine, and neurodegenerative diseases.

i3S is the project coordinator of GlycanTrigger and leads the unravelling of the cellular and molecular mechanisms of how changes in gut glycosylation activate innate and humoral immune responses. Furthermore, i3S is in charge of the project management, ethics, data management, gender equality, intellectual property rights, and in the consortium meetings organization.

Figure 11. Presentation of Consortium partners in the “About” section of the GlycanTrigger website

Work plan

The project is composed by 6 work packages (WP) that are interconnected to allow a continuous cross-communication, in a way that each WP supports and guides the others.

WP1

In WP1 we will define the gut glycome map — the composition of sugars (glycans) at the gut mucosa surface — of the transition from health to chronic inflammation. In this WP we will analyse the glycans composition of the gut glycocalyx along health to intestinal inflammation transition.

WP2

GlycanTrigger's WP2 studies how changes in the sugars on the surface of gut cells (called the glycocalyx) can affect the bacteria that live in our gut (microbiota). This WP is particularly interested in how these glycan changes might lead to microbiota alterations and to inflammation. By understanding these processes better, we hope to find ways to prevent or treat gut inflammation.

WP3

GlycanTrigger's WP3 looks at how changes in the sugars on the surface of cells in the gut can lead to activation of inflammation. This WP also looks at how these glycan changes might lead to the production of antibodies, which can further contribute to the inflammatory process. By studying these processes, we hope to gain a better understanding of how gut inflammation starts and how we might be able to stop it.

WP4

GlycanTrigger's WP4 intends to develop a preventive approach for counteracting changes in host mucosa glycome (glycocalyx) as a strategy to prevent perturbations in host-microbiota interactions associated with prevention of health to inflammation transition.

WP5

GlycanTrigger's WP5 develops a communication, dissemination and exploitation strategy with a set of activities, tools and materials, that include a website, in-hand dissemination tools, press releases, social media accounts, newsletters, podcast episodes, videos, scientific publications, organisation of project events and participation in non-project events. In addition, all relevant EFCCA sister organizations will be mapped and engaged, in order to maximise their involvement in the project. This WP is also responsible for implementing a patient empowerment-centred approach for an IBD transformative change.

WP6

GlycanTrigger's WP6 provides the consortium the leadership, management and administrative services, making sure all the other parts of the project run smoothly. This WP creates and implements a set of rules for financial and administrative management and ensure everyone follows them, complying with the rules of Horizon Europe. Moreover, a GlycanTrigger External Advisory Board is established as part of this WP to support the project's execution and offer insight and outside consultation.

Figure 12. Work plan in the “About” section of the GlycanTrigger website

Our impact

Scientific/Technological

New research on the role of glycans in inflammation and disease prevention leads to novel treatments and therapies. This knowledge helps medical professionals understand what triggers chronic inflammation and how to advise citizens to improve their health.

- Researchers and medical professionals understand the chronic inflammation factors triggering the health-to-disease transition and subsequently provide optimal counselling to citizens for improving their health.
- Health care professionals have access to and employ objective health indicators of chronic inflammation for monitoring the health status, establishing personalised prevention measures and improving the health outcomes for citizens.
- Health care professionals have the scientific evidence and understanding of health-to-disease transition to develop and use improved guidelines for personalised prevention strategies to tackle chronic diseases.

Figure 13. Expect impacts of the project in the “About” section of the GlycanTrigger website

2.3 ‘Our research’ page

This section will be the central dissemination channel for project progress. It will act as a repository for all non-confidential resources developed under the framework of the technical implementation, including:

- Project materials (technical reports, guidelines, informative sheets, etc.);
- Public deliverables;
- Scientific publications (all peer-reviewed articles, abstracts, posters, etc.);
- Useful links (including links to EFCCA associates, ECCO, etc.), in order to provide website visitors with additional sources of information.

This section will be updated according to the technical progress of the project and as soon as results are available.

2.4 ‘Patient Area’ page

This section is intended to provide accurate, reliable, evidence-based information about the disease to any visitor that wants to know more about IBDs. It is not the objective of the website to replace any medical advice or guidance, but instead to provide reliable (science-based) information, mostly to patients and families. All content will be developed by SPI (and eventually other partners) in straight collaboration with the coordinator (i3S) and partners, and will be specifically revised by clinical partners and EFCCA.

The section is currently under development (Figure 14). An example of informative content is provided in Figure 15.

Figure 14. “Patient Area” section of the GlycanTrigger website

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INFLAMMATORY BOWEL DISEASES

Ulcerative Colitis

- Inflammation is limited to the large intestine/colon
- Inflamed areas are continuous with no patchiness
- The pattern of inflammation is typically in the lower left abdomen
- Ulcers penetrate the inner lining of the abdomen
- Common bleeding during bowel movements

Crohn's Disease

- Inflammation is located anywhere in the gastrointestinal tract
- Patches of inflammation found in large sections of the bowel
- The pattern of inflammation is in the lower right abdomen
- Ulcers penetrate the entire thickness (several layers) of the abdominal lining
- Bleeding is uncommon

Figure 15. Example of content dedicated to patients and families

2.5 'Education and Training' page

This section will cover all activities and outputs related to patient empowerment, health literacy and guidelines. It will serve not only to support patients actively looking to know more about IBDs and IBD clinical management, but also to inform healthcare professionals on the recent developments of the project in these field. It will cover the following aspects:

- Training for change;
- Policy guidelines;
- GlycanTrigger podcast;
- FAQ.

This section will be updated according to the technical progress of the project and as soon as results are available.

2.6 'Media & Events' page

This section will include all outreach materials developed under the project, as well as news and events. It will be continuously updated according to project progress. A summary news about the kick-off meeting and the first press release of the project are already available.

2.7 Search tool

A search tool is available within the GlycanTrigger website. Figure 16 shows a representation of how it can be used.

Need a new search?

If you didn't find what you were looking for, try a new search!

Summary of Kick-off meeting

Figure 16. Search tool within the GlycanTrigger website

Chapter 3

Final Remarks

3. Final Remarks

The Deliverable 5.6 provides an overview of GlycanTrigger website structure and content. This is the main digital communication channel and will be used as a living and evolving outreach means to inform all target groups about the project, its background, activities and achievements.

This report describes the current version of the website, which will be further populated and updated as the technical execution of the project evolves. The project website reflects the objectives of the communication strategy described in deliverable D5.1 “Dissemination, Communication & Exploitation Plan 1” and may be modified according to our understanding of the needs of the target groups (especially patients and healthcare providers) and the updates of D5.1.

